

Are students being effectively transformed?

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The Indian Education Commission, prevalently known as Kothari Commission, 1964-66 makes several recommendations right from Early Child Care to University Education. One of them is the Continuous & Comprehensive Evaluation (CCE).

Of the two key aspects, the continuous factor caters to the growth and development of a child and dejects the judgment of child's performance on the basis of few periodic tests and/or through a single paper-pen examination. It further refutes that scoring 100 per cent signifies the student knows everything about the subject and scoring 0 per cent implies the student knows nothing in the area under discussion. It also takes into account, intra-examiner and inter-examiner inconsistency to the tune of 10% on the child's performance during a standard paper-pen examination. Apart from this, several other factors like stress, anxiety, well-being of a student, errors in question papers, etc. also impinge on the performance of a child.

The comprehensive factor includes scholastic and co-scholastic aspects. The scholastic facet involves academic subjects, work education, physical and health education, art education, etc. Co-scholastic aspects comprise participations and achievements of a child in a range of activities including literary & creative, scientific, aesthetic, fine arts, performing arts, dexterity, wits, team work, emotional skills, value system, etc., in each subject. This : i) reduces the workload on learners; ii) provides equal opportunities to each & every student in diversified areas; iii) facilitates those who are not good in academics but can flaunt their potential through athletics, sports, arts & culture; and iv) enables a novice to acquire skills through writings, oral presentations against a fairly

non-stop assessment criterion.

But, do the students really learn skills or just upload themselves with information? Are they truly endowed with talents to acquire proficiency? And do they comprehend whatever they have gathered so that they can make things happen? Though CCE have thrived in achieving the minimum levels of learning at all stages of education yet it could not do really well in attaining mastery in all competencies. Providing grades, instead of marks, could somehow shrink the intra examiner and inter examiner disparity in assessment, but failed to overcome the anxiety and fear of an examinee. Recording of evidences regarding psychomotor skills and evaluation of key qualities like regularity, punctuality, cleanliness, self-control, sense of duty, desire to serve, responsibility, fraternity, democratic attitude and sense of obligation to environmental protection are observed once in a blue moon.

The system that has reasonably done well, in transforming the conventional class-rooms (black board-chalk-duster culture) into a collaborative-cum-inter active course group at junior level, has turned out to be almost disastrous at higher level. With this system, students are mostly engaged in projects, assignments and presentations, thereby getting too little time to study. In a competitive world, where students get their passport to portals of higher learning, especially to professional porticos, on the basis of a few hundred theoretical multiple choice questions, grades no longer remain viable. In order to score more in competitive exams, either students move to a dummy college or carry out their CCE assignments by 'copy-paste method' without bothering for the contents or relevance of material.

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CCE, instead of making students more participative, expressive and inventive in the concerned subject, has become an instrument to grant liberal marks to bump up their overall percentile in the report cards.

What went wrong at the higher education level? The University Grants Commission prepared a roadmap to introduce CCE by the year 2012 at undergraduate level. But in states like M.P., the over-enthusiastic administration implemented the action plan suddenly in a single academic session that too without sensitizing the academic community and the stakeholders. The CCE should have been implemented step by step taking the feedback concurrently. Then, subject wise orientation of teachers should have been prearranged for the faculty before commencement of academic year. For the conduct of subject specific orientation, the UGC or DHE should have constituted subject-wise resource groups or have appointed pedagogical experts for each subject. Moreover, there should have been unit- and sub-unit wise list of concepts, teaching points, learning outcomes, core content, hard topics, minimum levels of

learning, mode of assessment, alternate mode of evaluation, etc. On this basis, universities should have published teachers' manual for each subject to make teachers familiar with various tools and techniques in evaluation. The Universities should have prepared resource persons to conduct workshops for framing quality questions, for setting quality question papers and for quality evaluation.

However, CCE was made compulsory and slapped on the academic fraternity without any ground work. And the most lamenting of all is that a student has to qualify the CCE before his/her final exams using any number of attempts. CCE does not mean that teachers have to go on administering test after test till the student passes. In fact, if a student fails in the first test, teachers should take remedial steps in the respective subjects and may allow, at the most, only one additional test. The secretarial guidelines are full of flaws and need to be reviewed methodically. CCE is an effective form of teaching, learning & evaluation and unless it is meticulously planned and directed it cannot produce tangible results.

Or we have simply turned the face ?

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